

ROOTS & BRANCHES

FRUIT AND FLOWERS: IMPACT

What systemic and cultural changes do we want to see in our communities and urban treescapes as a result of our work? e.g. collective guardianship of trees, improved tree equity, climate resilience and biodiversity

LEAVES: OUTCOMES AND ACHIEVEMENTS

What do we want our urban treescapes to look and feel like? e.g. more trees on our streets, edible hedgerows, increased knowledge of tree care

BRANCHES: ACTIVITIES AND ACTIONS

What do we do on a day-to-day or seasonal basis? e.g. tree planting, apple days, tree identification walks, arts and crafts

TRUNK: CORE WAYS OF WORKING

What approaches and practices provide the steady backbone of our work with communities? e.g. tree nurseries, tree guardians programme

SOIL: NOURISHMENT AND SUSTENANCE

What supports our projects to sustain and develop? e.g. fundraising, administration, strategic networks and relationships with our projects

ROOTS: BELIEFS AND VALUES

What beliefs and values form the strong foundation of our work with communities? e.g. environmental justice, the right to access to green space

Scan the QR code to find out more about the research project which informed this document and to view other useful tools

